

CHARACTERIZATION OF SABA VIRULENCE FACTOR OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI VIA IN-SILICO TOOLS

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Abstract

Helicobacter pylori infection of human gastrointestinal tract (GIT) largely depend on its attachment with stomach mucosal lining. This adherence is modulated by Sialic acid binding adhesion (SabA) protein. In current project, sequence of this protein was retrieved from Uniprot database and analyzed through SOPMA tool, AlphaFold database and MEME suite. The secondary (2D) configuration analysis showed alpha helix, extended strand, beta turn and random coil contents of 54.29, 11.04, 1.69 and 32.98%. Three dimensional (3D) structural analysis revealed highly complex folding in protein with two major domains. Seven conserved motifs. i. e., cpplenc, lcalsgc, atydkmkklaeelqaaqq, rnlamkkkedsehsaqh, atyndaktlseeisklph, ffgeskrw and fnsssdvw were found with significant p-values ($p < 0.05$). The conserved motifs unraveled in this project might help in designing drugs for inhibition of SabA binding with its receptors. In addition, the 2D and 3D configuration might also help in modification and blockage of this virulence factor thus reducing the *H. pylori* human infections

INTRODUCTION

Sialic acid binding adhesion (SabA) is surface protein of *Helicobacter pylori*. It established attachment between bacterium and stomach mucosal lining (Doohan et al. 2021). It binds with sialylated glycans found on mucosa (Benktander et al. 2018). This attachment leads to the infections caused by *H. pylori* including ulcers, gastritis and gastric cancer. As this

protein is associated with pathogenesis of bacterium, therefore, it is known as virulence factor (Sedarat et al. 2018). SabA protein exhibit inherent property of sialyl binding polymorphism (Aspholm et al. 2006). Gene encoding SabA virulence factor exhibits various single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). In addition, its gene conversion events confer diversity

to *H. pylori* and result in variations between outcome and severity of infection (Talarico 2012). A study documented *H. pylori* SabA protein distribution characteristics in several regions of China. Its prevalence was the highest in Guangxi (59.7%) followed by Hunan (52.2%), Heilongjiang (45.9%), Shandong (21.9%) and Qinghai (18.2%). “On status” of this gene was frequently found in bacteria from Guangxi, Hunan, Heilongjiang and Qinghai. i. e., 46.8, 47.8, 37.8 and 3.0%, respectively (Fang et al. 2022).

Polymorphism exhibited by SabA confers it different binding mechanisms for sialylated glycans. i. e., sLe^a, sdiLe^x and dialyllactosamine (sLn) (Yamaoka 2008). Among *H. pylori* isolated from Swedish clinical samples, 87% were capable of binding with all the three glycans and 39% with sialylated glycans. The 60% were capable of binding with sdiLe^x. Healthy stomach mucosal lining possess very low level of sialylated glycans as compared to *H. pylori* infected

mucosa. SabA binding epitopes affinity is determined by sialylation, fucosylation and core chain length (Walz et al. 2005).

Considering the significant association of SabA protein with *H. pylori* pathogenesis of human gastroduodenum region, we initiated current research targeting the characterization of SabA virulence factor. The characteristics explored might be used for inhibiting this protein from binding at its receptors, thus inhibiting the *H. pylori* infections.

2. Methodology

2.1 Sequence retrieval

The sequence of SabA virulence factor with accession ID A0A068LKR0 was retrieved from UNIPROT database (accessed in November 2024, available at <https://www.uniprot.org>). This protein comprises of 652 amino acids. Sequence of protein is given in Figure 1.

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MKKTILLSLSLASSLLNAEDNGFFVSAGYQIGEAVQMVKNTGELKNLNDKYEQLNQYLNQVASLKQSIRNA
NNIELVNSSLNLYLKSFTSNNYNSTTQSPIFNAVQAVITSVLGFWSLYAGNYFTFFVFNKDTKGSASVQGNPPF
RTIIDNCPGLENCGMDQATYDKMKKLAEEQLAAQQNATTKGNLNCALSGCATTNSTSNQPSSTVSSALNL
AQQLMDLIAKTKTAMMWKNIVISGVSNNVSGAITSTGYPTQYAVFNKAMIPILQQAVTLSQSNHTLSDSL
QAQATGSQTNPFKFAKDIYTFQAQNKQVISYAQDIFNLFNSIPAEQYKYLEKAYLKIPNAGQTPNTPYRQVVN
LNQEVQTIKNNVSYGNNRVDAALSVDVYNLKSQANIVATYNDAKTLSEEISKLPHNQVNTKDIVTLPY
DKNAPAAGQYNYQINPEQQSQLNQLAAMSNNPFKKGVMISSQNNNGAMNGLGVQVGYKQFFGESKR
WGLRYYGFFDYNHGYIKSSFFNSSSDVWVWYGGGSDLLVNIINDSITRKNKLSVGLFGGIQLAGTTWLNSQ
YVNLTAFFNNPYSAKVNASNFQFLFNLGLRTNLMKKKEDSEHSAQHGIELGIKIPTINTNYYSFLGTQLQYR
RLYSVYLNRYVFAY
    
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Figure 1: Sequence of SabA virulence factor retrieved from Uniprot database

2.2 Secondary (2D) configuration prediction

To analyze the secondary (2D) configuration of SabA protein, SOPMA tool NPS@ Network Protein Sequence Analysis (accessed in November 2024, available at https://npsa.lyon.inserm.fr/cgi-bin/secpred_sopma.pl) was employed and four aspects of 2D structure. i. e., alpha helix, beta pleated sheet, extended strand and random coil were predicted (Geourjon and Deleage 1995).

3.3 Three-dimensional (3D) configuration prediction

To assess the tertiary (3D) configuration of SabA protein, protein structure database, ALPHAFOLD

(accessed in November 2024, available at <https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk>) was consulted (Varadi and Velankar 2023).

3.4 Conserved motifs prediction

To assess the conserved motifs of SabA protein, Multiple Em for Motif Elicitation (MEME) suite (accessed in November 2024, available at <https://meme-suite.org/meme/tools/meme>) was consulted (Nystrom and McKay 2021). Sequence input was provided in type in format. For motif site distribution, any number of repetitions (anr) was selected.

4. Results

4.1 2D structure of SabA

SOPMA tool based analysis demonstrated the number of amino acids taking part in the formation of alpha helix, extended strand, beta sheet and random coil of SabA protein were 354, 72, 11 and 215, respectively (Figure 2 and Table 1).

Figure 2: Analysis of 2D configuration of SabA based on SOPMA tool

Table 1: Analysis of 2D configuration of SabA based on SOPMA tool

#	Component of 2D configuration	No. of amino acids	% age of amino acids
1	Alpha helix	354	54.29
2	Extended strand	72	11.04
3	Beta turn	11	1.69
4	Random coil	215	32.98

4.2 3D structure of SabA

AlphaFold database analysis revealed two distinct domains of protein SabA. One significantly

comprised of alpha helix and other of beta turns (Figure 2). Both these domains showed highly complex folding.

Figure 2: Analysis of tertiary (3D) configuration of SabA protein based on AlphaFold database

4.3 Conserved protein motifs prediction

Conserved motifs predicted for SabA protein included CPGLENC (p = 2.26e-10) and LCALSGC

(p = value 5.07e-9). The E-value for these two motifs was found 9.0e+000 and Bayers threshold was 8.33092 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Conserved protein motifs of SabA predicted through MEME suite

Three domains ATYDKMKKLAEEELQAAQQ (p = 6.94e-19), RTNLMKKKEDSEHSAQH (p = 5.59e-16) and ATYNDAKTLSEEISKLP (p = 2.60e-15) were found with E-value and Bayers threshold of 3.0e+001 and 6.94e-19, respectively. Two motifs,

FFGESKRW (p = 7.00e-12) and FNSSSDVW (p = 6.34e-9) were identified with E-value and Bayers threshold of 2.3e+002 and 8.32867, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Prediction of conserved domains of SabA alongwith E-value, Bayes threshold, p-value and motif sequence based on MEME suite

No. of motifs	E-value	Bayes threshold	p-value	Motifs sequence
1	9.0e+000	8.33092	2.26e-10	NPPFRTIIDN CPGLEN GMDQATKM
2			5.07e-9	QQNATTKG LCALSGC ATTNSTSNQ
3	3.0e+001	6.94e-19	6.94e-19	PGLENCGM ATYDKMKKLAEEELQAA NATTKGNN
4			5.59e-16	NFQFLFNLG RTNLMKKKEDSEHSA GIELGIKIPT
5			2.60e-15	NLKSQANI ATYNDAKTLSEEISKLP NQVNTKDIV
6	2.3e+002	8.32867	7.00e-12	GLGVQVGYK FFGESKR GLRYYGFFD
7			6.34e-9	YNHGYIKSSF FNSSDV TYGGGSDLL

4. Discussion

Exploration of 2D structure of SabA revealed the highest content of alpha helix. i. e., comprising of 354 amino acids. This is consistent with previous published data which reported high number (seven) alpha helices in this virulence factor (Benktander et al. 2018). Components of 2D structure in SabA are associated with its binding with stomach lining.

Stomach cells bear complicated molecules known as gangliosides. E. g., sialic acid and N-acetylactoseamine which are the binding targets for SabA. The 2D structure also plays role in attachment of this protein with fucosylated antigens.

Two domains were identified in 3D configuration of SabA virulence factor which is in accordance with previous literature. As per the previous data, there

are two prominent subunits of SabA. i. e., head and trans-membrane domain comprised of beta barrel. These two are linked with each other via handle domain which consists of alpha helix (Pang et al. 2014).

In current study, we found several conserved motifs as documented in literature. Previous reports demonstrated various conserved domains in C-terminal and tetratricopeptide regions of protein (Pang et al. 2014). These motifs are functionally potential because they serve as binding or active sites, as zinc finger regions, RNA binding regions, unwind DNA and RNA in the form of DEAD/DEAH box helicases (Emamjomeh 2019, Wong et al. 2015). Regions explored in this investigation might be significant for drug designing (Zhang et al. 2016). Characteristics of SabA explored in current project might be helpful in targeting this pathogenic factor via drug designing and genetic engineering alterations.

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